

Reviewing Cultural Heritage Catalyzing Role in Tourism Development Planning

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Abstract: The nature of tourism in any society is influenced by complex and intertwined economic, political, cultural, and social factors. Despite the significant and significant economic consequences of the tourism industry, many experts believe that tourism is more of a cultural phenomenon than an economic activity. Over the centuries, humans have transformed the natural environment into a landscape of cultural heritage using reason, hope, and hard work. These landscapes are priceless cultural heritage and are almost irreplaceable. As one of the ancient civilizations, Iran has a huge and impressive cultural heritage. One of the places that has an ancient history and civilization and has historical and ancient buildings and sites, etc. is Hamedan County. This county is a mountainous region and the highest county in Hamedan Province with an area of about 2300 square kilometers. This research attempts to help develop tourism in this ancient region by planning and presenting a strategy for developing the cultural heritage of the central part of Hamedan County. According to the results obtained and data analysis, the most important strategies for developing tourism resources in the research area and even in Hamedan County are to create a database of the status, type, and conditions of attractions in the research area for use in advanced plans and studies to fully identify tourism resources and plan for them.

Keywords: Tourism, Cultural Heritage, Sustainable Development, Iran, Hamedan, Statistics.

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1. Introduction:

Heritage is not only the past but also its symbol and representation, it speaks of the past, introduces us to ourselves, and outlines the future for us. Heritage can be both a foundation for unity and a source of conflict. How and in what form we use it determines its nature. Heritage can act as a tool and bring prosperity, comfort, and social self-esteem to the society in which it is located. If this asset is managed efficiently and effectively and developed sustainably, it can be a source of rich economic and socio-cultural benefits for the society in question (Norouzian et al., 2024). By developing heritage sites for tourism purposes, not only the budget required for the protection and maintenance of the site can be provided, but also the surrounding community can benefit from the positive economic approaches resulting from the presence of tourists (Qurraieet al., 2023). However, it should be noted that cultural heritage tourism can also create many challenges and issues for the local community, especially in developing countries, and adopting comprehensive management and empowering the local community can reduce many of these challenges and issues (Dehghan et al., 2024).

Iran has a 5,000-year-old cultural heritage that encompasses civilizations from different periods of human history. In terms of the existence of historical monuments, few countries can be compared to Iran. So much so that UNESCO has introduced Iran as one of the 10 most important countries in the world with valuable historical monuments (Khanian et al., 2013). Today, phenomena such as tourism have moved away from being a political tool and have become a natural flow of cultural exchange. Hamedan is, without exaggeration or speculation, one of the oldest habitats and origins of the children of Iran. This land is the vastness of Iranian history. But what is left of Greater Hamedan today except for signs in history books and buildings that are facing destruction, and memories and melodies in beliefs, rituals, and voices that are beautifully written on the tongues of the men and women of this land and indicate the lifestyles of the people of this region (Aydin et al., 2020)?

The historical tourist attractions of Hamedan are a collection of monuments from different periods, some of which (such as the ancient caves of Darband in Hamedan) date back more than 100,000 years. One of the places that has housed many historical monuments is the central part of Hamedan County. In this study,

we will address the challenges facing it, so that these valuable historical monuments can attract more tourists with appropriate planning. (Norouzian & Gheitarani, 2023). To understand what remains of this great legacy, we must take firm steps and gather the achievements of the scholars' research and studies and hand them over to the younger generation and the generation that will inherit this land (Gheitarany et al., 2013). Today, the tourism industry is one of the top three industries in the world in terms of employment creation and foreign exchange earnings. Tourism is a fundamental factor for the economic, social, cultural, and political development and progress of regions, as well as one of the most prosperous ways to spend free time (Aghazadeh Dizaji, 2017; Gheitarani et al., 2020).

This industry, which is referred to as the invisible industry, has led to the comprehensive development of regions, created countless jobs, and improved the level of knowledge and awareness of people, and for this reason, it is considered an important phenomenon in facilitating development. Visiting cultural and historical resources is one of the largest, most comprehensive, and fastest-growing sectors of the tourism industry of the present era (Maleki et al., 2024; Gheitarani et al., 2024). Heritage tourism appears to be growing much faster than other forms of tourism, especially in developing countries and should be considered as a potentially important tool for poverty reduction and economic development. Heritage tourism usually relies on living and built elements of culture and uses the tangible and intangible past as a resource for tourism. Although interest in heritage tourism is growing day by day, it is a nascent field. There is still a lack of integrated research on the dynamics of cultural heritage tourism in developing regions (Farrokhirad & Gheitarani, 2024).

2. Theoretical

The product of heritage tourism. Researchers and managers divide it into different types to facilitate research, knowledge creation, marketing, planning, and management of tourism impacts. Just as tourism is often divided into forms such as nature-based, heritage, health, and adventure, heritage tourism can also be divided into sectors and types to show its complexities and understand its distinctive features (Gheitaraniet al., 2024). This division is usually made from both supply and demand perspectives. That is, the types of heritage tourism (and tourism in general) can be defined by the places, events, and human artifacts that are observed or visited (i.e. consumed) and also by the motivations and activities of the tourists who visit (consume) them. Research suggests that in most cases, people visit heritage sites to enhance learning, satisfy curiosity, grow spiritually, feel comforted, get away from home, spend time with loved ones, or find themselves (Dizaji et al., 2023).

Heritage Tourists are divided into three groups based on their motivation: culturally oriented, culturally sensitive, and culturally aware. These motivations, together with the remnants of the past, create a range of types of heritage tourism, all of which are an important part of the heritage product in countries (GHADARJANI & GHEITARANI, 2013). These three groups differ considerably in terms of behavior, experience, and interpretation. Culturally oriented tourists spend more time at the site, travel more nights away from home, and consider visiting archaeological sites as their main activity (Dizaji, 2024- a, b).

And give more importance to interpretation. This group is more satisfied with their trip and understands the importance of site conservation. Culturally sensitive tourists are more similar to

culture-oriented tourists than to culture-aware tourists (Naghbi Iravani et al., 2024). For culture-aware tourists, unlike the other two groups, walking and taking pictures are the main activities. Major challenges in cultural heritage conservation (Norouzian, & Gheitarani, 2024). The major challenges faced by less developed countries in cultural heritage conservation can be summarized as follows: Financial constraints, ownership issues, encroachment by farmers, looting and illegal excavations, colonialism, inadequate conservation, war and conflict, modernization, the innumerable number of heritage sites, lack of cooperation and holistic management, and lack of social and political will (Norouzian and Gheitarani, 2025).

The National Committee of ICOMOS. The International Council on Historic Monuments and Sites went through a 35-year process and finally came to fruition in 1965. Later it was known as ICOMOS and now it is active in Iran with more than 100 national committees and 20 scientific committees worldwide (Abbaszadeh et al., 2015). The International Council on Historic Monuments and Sites, which was formed in Warsaw in 1965, is defined as a non-governmental organization on a broad scale and is the most important international authority that works professionally in the field of protection of historic monuments and sites (Naghbi Iravani et al., 2024). The headquarters of this organization is located in Paris. ICOMOS Iran was officially formed on April 19, 2004, and began its activities. Following the formation of the International Council on Historic Buildings and Sites, studies and research in various fields of this field were given the attention of its trustees and became one of the important goals of the Council, to the extent that the activity of more than 20 ICOMOS scientific committees in the world now confirms this (Norouzian and Gheitarani, 2025; Kahvand & Ghadarjani, 2015).

Among the international scientific committees of ICOMOS are the International Specialized Committee on Cultural Tourism, Historic Gardens and Sites, Stone Restoration, Wood Restoration, Historic Cities, Brick Architecture, and Underwater Cultural Heritage (Norouzian et al., 2024). These committees are responsible for developing international guidelines and charters in each of the approaches related to the protection, research, restoration, and presentation of immovable heritage, which requires gaining knowledge of the latest advances in human knowledge in that field (Sultan Qurraie et al., 2022). The ICOMOS statutes do not consider any limitations for the formation of these committees, and they are formed in different fields at the discretion of the ICOMOS Executive Committee (Karimimansoob et al., 2024). This council, which was the result of the idea of creating an international organization based on national committees at the 1930 Rome International Conference, became more fruitful at the 1931 Athens Conference, and in the following years, it became systematic and manifested at the global level in 1965 under the name ICOMOS (Sarabi et al., 2023).

At the Athens Conference, the issue of the protection and restoration of cultural, historical, and artistic monuments was examined and led to a resolution that was then known as the Athens Charter due to the importance of its provisions. The goals, principles, and criteria envisaged in the Athens Charter attracted the attention of the League of Nations as a comprehensive global organization responsible for world peace and security (Norouzian and Gheitarani, 2023). To establish international cooperation and protection of historical monuments and buildings, a commission called the International Commission on Monuments was

established by the League of Nations in 1933, to continue the path planned at the Athens Conference (Ghadarjan et al., 2013; Gheitarani et al., 2013).

The objectives of the aforementioned commission were to strive for international cooperation and protection of the cultural and historical heritage of countries through the development of recommendations, the provision of necessary specialized training, the promotion of public awareness of the values of such works, the development of laws governing their protection at the national level, and the development of global treaties for the international protection of cultural heritage (Zakerhaghighi et al., 2015). In 1954, this commission proposed that the concept of historic monument be applied to buildings whose preservation is of social interest and is considered valuable, especially from the point of view of art history. Currently, the International Council on Historic Monuments and Sites in Iran is carrying out activities in the field of harmonizing the status of cultural heritage with global standards and eliminating gaps such as the development of a restoration charter (Samami et al., 2024; Saba Sultan Qurraie, 2024).

Principles of the Cultural Tourism Charter (Tourism Management in Heritage Places). The following is the eighth draft of the International Tourism Charter, International Commission, International Council on Monuments and Sites (ICOMOS), prepared for adoption at the 12th General Assembly of ICOMOS, Mexico, October 1999. Since domestic and international tourism is one of the most important venues for cultural exchange, environmental protection should provide responsible and guided opportunities for members of the host community and visitors to experience and understand first-hand the heritage and culture of that community (Norouzian & Sarabi, 2023).

- The natural and cultural heritage is a material and spiritual reserve that tells the story of the historical development of a society. This heritage plays an important role in modern life and should be accessible to the public in an objective, intellectual, and emotional way. Conservation programs for natural features and intangible aspects, contemporary cultural manifestations, and the overall context should facilitate the recognition and understanding of the significance of the heritage in a way that is understandable and accessible to the host and tourist community (Norouzian, 2024; Sohrabi, 2024).
- Individual aspects of cultural heritage are at different levels of importance. Some are of universal value and others are of national, regional, or local importance. Interpretation programs should communicate that significance in a way that is relevant and accessible to the host and tourist community, through stimulating forms of education, media, and modern technology, and through personal interpretation of historical, environmental, and cultural information. Interpretation programs should raise public awareness, and encourage and support the long-term survival of the natural and cultural heritage (Arash Sohrabi, 2024).
- Interpretation programs should explain the significance of heritage sites, traditions, and cultural practices in the context of past experiences and the difficulties of the current situation of the region and the host society, including the difficulties of cultural and linguistic minority groups. The visitor should always be aware of the different cultural values that may be attributed to a particular heritage resource (Zaker Haghighi et al., 2014).

The relationship between heritage sites and tourism is a dynamic one and can involve conflicting values. This relationship should be managed in a way that is sustainable for present and future generations. Places of heritage significance have intrinsic value for people as an important basis for cultural diversity and social development (Khanian et al., 2019). The long-term preservation and conservation of living cultures, heritage sites, collections, and their natural and indigenous integrity and context should be a central component of social, economic, political, legal, cultural, and tourism development policies. The interaction between heritage resources or values and tourism is a dynamic and changing interaction that creates opportunities, challenges, and potential conflicts (Akbarzadeh et al., 2016).

Tourism developments, activities, and projects should have positive outcomes and minimize negative impacts on the heritage and lifestyle of the host community while responding to the needs and aspirations of tourists. Tourism conservation, promotion, and development programs should be based on a comprehensive understanding of the distinct but often complex and contradictory aspects of the heritage significance of a particular place (Sultan Qurraie et al., 2022). Ongoing research and consultation are important to enhance recognition and understanding of that significance. It is important to preserve the authenticity of heritage sites and collections (Naghbi Iravani et al., 2024).

This is a key element of their cultural significance, as it is reflected in the natural material of shared memory and the intangible traditions that remain from the past. Programs should promote and explain the authenticity of places and cultural experiences to increase recognition and understanding of cultural heritage. Tourism and infrastructure development plans should take into account the artistic, social, and cultural dimensions, natural and cultural landscapes and biodiversity features, and the wider visual context of heritage sites (Karimimansoob et al., 2024). Priority should be given to the use of local products and local architectural styles or indigenous and local traditions should be taken into account. Before heritage sites are protected and developed for tourism, management plans should assess the natural and cultural values of the site. These plans should then determine appropriate levels of acceptable change – particularly about the impact of visitor numbers on the natural features, integrity, ecology, and biodiversity of the site, local road and transport systems, and the social, economic, and cultural well-being of the host community.

If the potential level of change is unacceptable, proposed development plans should be modified. It is essential to develop ongoing evaluation programs to assess the incremental impacts of tourism and development activities on the site or the specific community. Conservation and Tourism Planning Heritage sites should be a worthwhile, satisfying, and enjoyable visit for the tourist. Conservation and tourism plans should provide high-quality information to enhance the visitor's understanding of the importance of the heritage features and the need to conserve them so that they can enjoy their visit in a way that is appropriate to the site. Visitors, if they wish, should be able to visit the site at their own pace. It may be necessary to establish specific routes to minimize the impact of visits on the integrity and natural fabric of a site and its natural and cultural features. Respecting the sanctity of sites and religious customs and traditions is of paramount importance to site managers, visitors, policymakers, planners, and tour operators. Visitors should be encouraged to respect the values and way of life of the host community as valued guests and to

refrain from stealing cultural objects or illegally trading them. And to behave responsibly so that they are welcomed back if they wish to return.

Planning of tourism activities should provide appropriate facilities for the comfort, safety, and well-being of the visitor, so that the enjoyment of the visit is enhanced, but does not have a detrimental impact on important components or features of the local environment. Host communities and indigenous peoples should be involved in conservation and tourism planning. The rights and resources of the host community at local and regional levels, property owners and indigenous peoples concerned who may exercise traditional rights or responsibilities over the land and its significant sites should be respected. They should be involved in setting objectives, strategies, and protocols for the identification, conservation, management, presentation, and interpretation of their resources, cultural traditions, and contemporary cultural manifestations in the context of tourism. While the heritage of a particular place or region may have a global dimension, the needs and desires of some communities or localities regarding the limitation or management of the physical, spiritual, or intellectual access of visitors to certain traditions, knowledge, beliefs, activities, objects or cultural sites should be respected.

Tourism activities and conservation should be for the benefit of the host community. Policymakers should support measures for the equitable distribution of the benefits of tourism so that all regions of the country benefit. This will improve levels of socio-economic development and contribute to poverty reduction, where necessary. Conservation management and tourism activities should provide equitable economic, social, and cultural benefits to men and women of the host or local community, at all levels, through education, training, and the creation of full-time employment opportunities.

A significant proportion of income from tourism to heritage sites should be allocated to the conservation, preservation, and presentation of those sites, including their natural and cultural setting. Visitors should, wherever possible, benefit from this allocation in the current situation of the region and the host society, including the difficulties of cultural and linguistic minority groups. The visitor should always be aware of the different cultural values that may be attributed to a particular heritage resource. The relationship between heritage sites and tourism is a dynamic one and can involve conflicting values. This relationship should be managed in a way that is sustainable for present and future generations. Places of heritage significance have intrinsic value for people as an important basis for cultural diversity and social development. The long-term preservation and conservation of living cultures, heritage sites, collections, and their natural and indigenous integrity and context should be a central component of social, economic, political, legal, cultural, and tourism development policies. The interaction between heritage resources or values and tourism is a dynamic and changing interaction that creates opportunities, challenges, and potential conflicts.

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research and consultation are important to enhance recognition and understanding of that significance. It is important to preserve the authenticity of heritage sites and collections. This is a key element of their cultural significance, as it is reflected in the natural material of shared memory and the intangible traditions that remain from the past. Programs should promote and explain the authenticity of places and cultural experiences to increase recognition and understanding of cultural heritage. Tourism and infrastructure development plans should take into account the artistic, social, and cultural dimensions, natural and cultural landscapes and biodiversity features, and the wider visual context of heritage sites.

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Conservation management and tourism activities should provide equitable economic, social, and cultural benefits to men and women of the host or local community, at all levels, through education, training, and the creation of full-time employment opportunities. A significant proportion of income from tourism to heritage sites should be allocated to the conservation, preservation, and presentation of those sites, including their natural and cultural setting.

Table 1. The Role of Cultural Tourism Planning in Tourism Development in Hamadan County

	Frequency	Percentage	valid percentage	Cumulative percentage
Very high	134	9/34	9/34	9/34
High	146	0/38	0/38	9/27
Moderate	104	0/27	0/27	0/100
Total	384	0/100	0/100	

Tourists consider the role of planning in tourism development to be very important in their choices. Tourists in Hamadan County have assigned the first option to Very High with 53.9%, High with 33.9% in the next rank, and Medium with 12.2% in the next priorities.

Table 2. The role of planning in tourism development

Description	Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Cumulative percentage
Very much	207	9/53	9/53	9/53
High	130	9/33	9/33	8/87
Average	47	2/12	2/12	100
Total	384	100	100	

Tourism is considered the third most profitable industry in the world, a clean industry that is considered one of the factors of income generation and economic prosperity in many countries today. The transportation system (air, rail, sea, and road), hoteliers, travel service offices, natural and artificial attractions, stores and shopping centers, and welfare facilities and construction in a country form the links of the large chain of the tourism industry, and each of them plays a role in the prosperity and development of this income-generating industry. The small province of Hamedan is considered rich in terms of cultural and natural attractions. Because of its many capabilities such as having a coastline of 280 kilometers, being in a suitable geographical location and connecting Europe and Asia, as well as historical attractions and the existence of more than 950 historical monuments in the province, it is expected that tourism will be prosperous, income-generating and job-creating.

One of the regions with rich historical monuments is Hamadan County, some of which are over 100,000 years old. Monuments such as caves and rock shelters, hills, historical residential areas, etc. For this reason, tourists have evaluated the role of these attractions in attracting tourists and developing these areas by more than 95%. Unfortunately, historical monuments in our country are of less importance than other attractions, and Hamadan County is no exception to this rule. Historical monuments in this county are also facing the threat of destruction due to some irregularities, and if these problems cannot be resolved according to principled planning and proper management, the loss of these ancient capitals will practically destroy the past of this land and landscape. Lack of accommodation, inadequate access roads, and insufficient

advertising are some of the reasons for the lack of tourism development, which tourists have assessed as 97%, 98%, and 99%, respectively.

Another major problem facing these places is the weakness of macro-management and the lack of a comprehensive and well-organized plan for the preservation and restoration of such historical structures. 98.5% of tourists have also highlighted the role of planning for the development of heritage tourism. The destruction and erosion of these places by environmental conditions imposed on the structures, such as rain and wind, etc., and pollution, such as air pollution, incomplete fuel from industrial plants, incomplete fuel, and the indiscriminate use of polluting gasoline and diesel-burning vehicles, such as light and heavy vehicles, smoking, and lighting candles in closed historical spaces. The result of air pollution is the production of destructive gases such as carbon dioxide, sulfur dioxide, ozone, carbon monoxide, etc., which are converted into acids during a chemical reaction and cause irreparable damage to the monument. Noise pollution and vibrations from cars, etc. seriously endanger historical monuments. The large number of visitors to a historical space, direct contact of people with historical monuments, causes damage to the building, including abrasion and destruction of the monument, and an increase in the percentage of humidity around and inside the building, and . . . 99% of tourists who enter this area consider the frequent use of such places a threat to its survival.

3. Findings

Hamdan city is one of the foothill cities of Hamedan province, located on the slopes of the Alborz and Alvand mountains, on the

banks of the Sefidrood River, and along the dense olive groves. This geographical location has created a unique landscape of a combination of urban development and nature. This city is a transit city. For this reason, many travelers make a short stop there to buy Hamadan's main product, olives and its products. The climate of this city, which is located in the south of Hamedan province, is Mediterranean, with mild and slightly humid winters and hot and dry summers. Hamadan city has a history of six thousand years and has hills, buildings, and... It has a rich history, in addition to other attractions such as very attractive views on the heights covered with evergreen olive trees, and Guarao mineral waters are one of

the potential areas for tourism. The questionnaire of this research was completed during the spring holidays of 2013 in Hamadan city by 384 tourists entering this area. At this time, according to official statistics from the Cultural Heritage, Tourism and Handicrafts Organization of Hamedan Province, the total number of tourists entering this area from Hamedan Province is estimated to be 108 thousand people, which includes most of the passing travelers.

Gender of tourists. The number of female tourists in this area at the time of the research was 47.1% and the number of male tourists was 52.9%. Its frequency and percentage are included in Table (3).

Table 3. Gender of tourists in Hamadan city

Description	Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Cumulative percentage
Male	203	9.52	9/52	9/52
Female	181	1.47	1/47	100
Total	384	100	100	

4. Discussion

Developing tourism at heritage sites can bring more income and higher standards of living to residents. These sites can play an important role in the economic development of the region. However, a concern with tourism at historical sites is that some sites are located in remote areas, such that tourists to these areas are usually day trippers and spend little money on the site itself or its surroundings. The best way to solve this problem is to increase the length of stay of tourists and add value to the heritage sites. Tourists in Hamedan city have assessed the role of tourism development in increasing income and employment by more than 85%. Since the protection of cultural heritage is not limited to the experts of the heritage organization but relies on public opinion, local managers, who are responsible for most of the important decisions, have all been responsible for the protection of cultural heritage.

According to the analyzed questionnaires, it can be stated that a better understanding of the attraction of cultural heritage is a step towards increasing the number of tourists to these areas. This also requires long-term planning through advertising, creating appropriate roads, building tourism facilities, etc. In such historical contexts, it can be hoped that such places in Hamedan City will encounter a large number of enthusiastic and cultural tourists.

Understanding cultural heritage attracts tourists to this area. In the first hypothesis, considering that the average was taken from questions 12, 13, 17, and 18, based on the analysis of the data obtained through one-sample t-test, it was determined that there is a statistically significant difference between the average scores of the set of questions on the indicators (knowledge of the cultural heritage of the region, the existence of historical villages in the region, the impact of advertising and planning) in the development of heritage tourism, meaning that the people participating in this study consider the existence of these indicators to be necessary and effective.

Table 4. One-Sample Test

One-Sample Statistics				
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
F1	384	1.8737	.85845	.04381

One-Sample Test						
Test Value = 0						
	T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
F1	42.77	383	.000	1.87	1.7876	1.9598

Table 5. First hypothesis

	Observed N	Expected N	Residual
1. 00	134	32. 0	102. 0
1. 25	9	32. 0	-23. 0
1. 50	45	32. 0	13. 0
1. 75	19	32. 0	-13. 0
2. 00	32	32. 0	. 0
2. 25	41	32. 0	9. 0
2. 50	31	32. 0	-1. 0
2. 75	1	32. 0	-31. 0
3. 00	25	32. 0	-7. 0
3. 25	27	32. 0	-5. 0
3. 50	3	32. 0	-29. 0
3. 75	17	32. 0	-15. 0
Total	384		

Planning for cultural heritage tourism leads to the development of regional tourism. In the second hypothesis, the average of questions 14, 15, and 16 were taken and the statistical data was analyzed and determined through the one-sample t-test. A significant difference is seen between the average scores of the set

of questions of the indicators (lack of accommodations and places of residence, non-standard and frequent visits, and the level of knowledge and planning of cultural tourism) in the development of heritage tourism.

Table 6. One-Sample Test

One-Sample Statistics				
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
F2	384	1. 7995	.79745	.04069

One-Sample Test						
Test Value = 0						
	T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
F2	44. 22	383	.000	1. 799	1. 72	1. 88

Table 7. Second hypothesis

	Observed N	Expected N	Residual
1. 00	158	42. 7	115. 3
33	14	42. 7	-28. 7
1. 67	6	42. 7	-36. 7
2. 00	103	42. 7	60. 3
2. 33	17	42. 7	-25. 7
2. 67	14	42. 7	-28. 7
3. 00	63	42. 7	20. 3
3. 33	2	42. 7	-40. 7
3. 67	7	42. 7	-35. 7
Total	384		

5. Conclusion

Creating the necessary facilities and equipment in tourism resources and attractions in forests, river, mountainous areas, and tourism model areas such as Bahar as priorities for the development of the tourism industry in the research area. Creating the necessary conditions to protect existing tourism attractions in mountainous forest areas and tourism model areas Defining the Ganjnameh axis and conducting its studies as an executive priority at the research area level Creating suitable conditions for the development of tourism model areas in the research area as tourist attraction points to attract and increase the duration of stay of tourists, especially in the tourism model areas of Malayer, Bahar, Ghahavand, and Hamedan due to the high volume of tourists Improving the quantitative and qualitative level of forest mountainous areas and tourism model areas in the research area to attract more tourists. Using the attraction of the river and the Malayer dam reservoir, considering its long extension and parallelism with the main Hamedan axis. Providing conditions for creating facilities and installations in tourism resources and attractions, especially in the Ganjnameh axis

- Identifying tourism capacities of Hamadan County with the approach of handicrafts in the research area
- Introducing tourism resources and attractions in the research area in regional dimensions.
- Developing appropriate time plans to exploit all resources and attractions in the research area with the approach of using mountain, forest, and river resources.
- Monitoring and reviewing resources and attractions that are deficient in terms of capacity and range and resolving acute issues in terms of the environment and so on to increase the level of attraction.
- Monitoring relevant agencies on the use of resources and attractions and evaluating and controlling the negative effects of the presence of tourists in the research area.
- Developing plans to create tourist recreation centers in forest-mountainous areas, taking into account environmental issues and environmental conditions.

6. References

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